

*Climate and cultural based design and market valuable
technology solutions for Plus Energy Houses*

Evaluation framework for PEBs

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1 Executive summary

This report reviews the state of the art literature about PEB definition and metrics. A definition of Positive Energy Building (PEB) is proposed along with a consistent evaluation framework for performance assessment of solution sets applied to PEB design.

First, a comprehensive literature review of existing PEB definition, looking for common patterns across different approaches in terms of domain boundaries, role of energy efficiency, renewable energy and environmental sustainability, as well as effect of evaluation method on the energy balance.

Then, a robust and holistic definition of PEB is outlined according to Cultural-E principles, by taking into account the positive energy balance and environmental sustainability goals.

Finally, a consistent evaluation framework for assessing performance of solution sets for PEB is proposed.

Appropriate leading and lagging Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been selected from literature and corresponding calculation methodologies are summarized and referenced. Qualitative and quantitative KPIs related to Energy, Load matching, Grid Interaction, Indoor Environmental Quality, Environment, Economic and Social impacts are discussed. Smart Readiness Indicator is also included.

2 Introduction

The scope of this deliverable is to define a consistent evaluation framework for PEB building design, which include to identify proper PEB definition and to design and develop a KPIs evaluation framework as decision support tool for PEB design.

The evaluation framework is a fundamental contribution to the definition of PEB tailored solution sets and business models. The purpose of the framework is to evaluate performance of solution sets proposed in Cultural-E project, for different building size and climate cultural clusters.

Towards that scope, a list of KPIs is proposed and classified under different categories related to plus energy balance, indoor environment quality, climate resiliency, life cycle costs and environmental impact in order to address the needs of building designer.

The main objectives of the deliverable are summarised below:

- To identify PEB definition based on literature review and Cultural-E project goals
- To list suitable KPIs based on different categories in order to address designer requirements
- To design and develop the PEB evaluation framework in order to be applied to solution sets evaluation and facilitate designers in decision making process

As a side note, based on literature review results and according to the cooperation with the sister projects EXCESS and syn.ikia, the original designation PEH – Plus Energy House stated in the Project Agreement was aligned to PEB – Positive Energy Building.

An open access paper is attached as Annex I. It reports detailed results of literature review on the existing PEB definitions and how different studies answered to key question related to the physical boundary, balance contribution, time span, metrics for evaluating PEB, PEB balance, and other requirements related to energy efficiency, indoor climate, load matching and grid interaction, and economic and environmental aspects.

3 State of the art on PEB definition

A systemic work was carried out to identify relevant literature on PEB by selecting high quality papers encompassing balance between load and generation, or energy import/export. Papers not presenting energy saving and RES contribution, or focusing on community level were discarded.

A full review to extract the key parameters to evaluate PEB, such as metrics of balance, period of balance, type of energy use, type of energy balance, renewable energy (RE) supply options, Load Matching (LM) and Grid Interaction (GI) indicators and final energy balance, was completed.

Details are described in Annex I.

Literature review confirmed an increased attention towards the Plus Energy Building concept within the building community and national building codes. Studies on PEBs indicated that these buildings have the potential to drastically reduce the energy consumption while increasing the total share of RE thus they represent a promising strategy in the aim of decarbonizing the building sector. In the literature, the concepts are expressed using a variety of terms and phrases whereas the assessment approaches are not consistent in terms of key aspects to be considered while evaluating PEB, as the contribution to the balance. The main conclusion from the literature review is that a consistent definition and framework is still missing.

The review discussed the widely used metric for evaluating PEB, balancing period, the type of energy included in the balance, the type of balance and the RE supply options, as well as other parameters related to the interaction between the building and the energy grid, as well as the environmental and economic aspects.

4 PEB definition

In Cultural-E approach, a clear definition of PEB, including domain and time frame for the calculation, should include the concept of positive energy balance and a null contribution of consumed energy to CO₂ emissions. In other words, the new building should be a sustainable prosumer.

Stated the considerable variability of existing approaches emerged from literature review, Cultural-E approach is to propose a flexible definition that could take into consideration several parameters that may affect the final balance of the building, such as building type, functionality, and location.

In Cultural-E project, the objective is to provide benchmarks and reference methodologies for evaluating the KPIs starting from the experience of the four case studies located in different climate cultural clusters within the European context.

As a general requirement, PEBs shall produce more energy than they consume to compensate for the negative energy balance of surrounding buildings, thus contributing to the overall reduction of GHG emissions of the neighbourhood. The uptake of PEBs represent a key step towards the decarbonization of the building sector. Furthermore, they shall contribute to energy flexibility allowing for buildings to act synergically as an integrated part of the energy system and exchange energy (electrical, thermal energy, or other future energy carriers) among them in energy communities or with the grid.

Different levels of evaluation can be identified:

1. **Compliance assessment:** in compliance with most building related EU and national standard requirements and criteria for the evaluation (e.g., primary energy, CO₂eq emission, weighting factors, etc.).
2. **Operative assessment:** based on measured final energy balance between delivered and exported energy calculated for each energy vector, key performance indicators and performance evaluations.
3. **Sustainability assessment:** based on overall building life cycle, including the total energy required for daily operations, user related consumption, and to build, produce materials as well as demolish the building.

Relevant considerations detailed in Annex I led to choose the operational assessment methodology, applicable to both building design and operational phase.

According to the operational assessment, the Plus Energy Building is an energy-efficient building that produces more final energy than it uses, including building operation and user-related consumption, via locally available RE sources over a time span of one year

while ensuring the lowest CO_{2eq} emissions, high user satisfaction with indoor environment quality, good dynamic matching, according to economic affordability and to technical viability.

The energy balance is based on measured or predicted final energy between load and generation related to each single energy vector. The energy generation shall be performed by RE systems located within building footprint and can be extended to adjacent lots if there is a physical connection and direct control of RE generation system relying on ownership of the buildings or lots, neighbourhood grid infrastructure, and building management. Besides the plus energy balance verification, PEBs shall ensure minimal costs for the environment and added value to final users by exploiting building flexibility to reduce the stress on the power grid, favour low carbon emissions, foster accessible, comfortable, and healthy indoor environments, and ease access to e-mobility.

The building operation represents the energy consumption for keeping the dwellings in livable conditions and includes heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water, lighting, and auxiliaries. Energy uses contribution to energy balance are reported in table 1.

Table 1: Energy uses considered in the operative assessment level.

	Assessment level: operative
Heating	Y
Cooling	Y
DHW	Y
Ventilation	Y
Auxiliary	Y
Lighting	Y
Plug loads	Y
EV charging	N
Embodied Energy	N
	Y: included in the balance
	N: Not included in the balance

For details on hypothesis and rationale of PEB definition please see Annex I.

According to the definition, PEB targets can be summarized as:

- Positive energy balance (by energy efficiency and RES energy production)
- Environmental sustainability

These main targets are described in the paper and will be specified into KPIs target values in D4.7. Climate resilience will be also included in the evaluation of solution sets.

5 PEB evaluation framework

Based on Cultural-E findings, different technologies developed in Cultural-E project and market available technologies could be integrated by a designer, then the resulting solution set may be introduced in the design of a new PEB building.

Only few solution sets allow the designer to meet the targets on energy efficiency and environmental sustainability stated in the PEB definition, thus a set of indicators and calculation methodologies were identified in order to assess plus energy balance and environmental impact at operative scale and for the life span. Then, the analysis of implications related to the energy balance led to consider load matching and grid interaction performance.

Furthermore, solution sets are not equivalent under other relevant aspects, as the building must be sustainable also towards economic and social impacts, indoor environment quality (IEQ), health and wellbeing, and smart readiness.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are the proper means to evaluate performance toward specific intended targets. These critical indicators provide a focus for strategic and operational improvement, create an analytical basis for decision making process and help focus attention on what matters most. They are intended for the design phase, but most of them can also apply to later monitoring and verification steps.

KPIs can track efficiency, quality, compliance, behaviours, economics or resource utilization which comes from concepts behind Cultural-E project:

- Households' interactions with the building and systems, designed to avoid energy waste, improve indoor environmental quality and increase liveability
- Viability, performance and replicability of technologies for heating, cooling, indoor air quality and grid connection, including GHG reduction and plus energy target
- Affordability compared to nZEB buildings
- Ability of PEB to face climate and cultural changes, like climate change or new needs of electric vehicle charge, or to cooperate in clusters.

Designing a PEB with reference to KPIs includes setting the desired level of performance and benchmarking the proposed solution against that targets.

KPIs are divided in two classes. Leading indicators are precursors of future success in the design; lagging indicators show how successful the designer was at achieving results. Designing with KPIs means working to improve leading indicators during the design phase, that will later drive lagging benefits, during monitoring and verification phase. Leading indicators are used to estimate performances of a given solution set,

but lagging indicators give a designer the opportunity to identify lessons learned and improve. The analysis of both are a key aspect in Cultural-E approach.

5.1 KPIs classification and definition

Classification is required in order to organize the KPIs in different categories and use them according to designer needs.

Based on literature review and Cultural-E project objectives, the KPIs have been categorized in seven main categories, namely:

- Energy
- Load matching and Grid Interaction
- IEQ
- Environmental impact
- Economic impact
- Social Impact
- Smart Readiness

The definition of the KPIs depends on the specific objectives, goals, and criteria. Appropriate KPIs for this evaluation framework were collected, processed and interpreted by an extensive literature investigation, which is discussed in the Annex I. KPIs were selected and characterized by:

- Name and optional acronym
- An optional short description, to describe the function clearly
- Type (leading, lagging KPI)
- Calculation method: a formula, when available, to make clear the KPI operation
- Source/references
- Range for the metric

Indicators for Energy are reported in table 2.

Table 2: Energy KPIs

Name	Description	Type	Calculation method	Source	Metric range
Primary energy	Annual primary energy use	Leading (simulation)	Calculated from delivered and exported energy for each energy carrier. Based on ISO energy performance indicator	ISO 16346:2013	
Final energy		Leading (simulation) Lagging (monitoring)	Calculation/Measurement on each energy carrier		

Load matching (how local energy generation matches building load) and Grid interaction (the energy exchange between the building and a power grid) are described by KPIs in table 3.

Table 3 Load matching and Grid interaction KPIs

Name	Description	Type	Calculation method	Source	Metric range
self-generation (load cover factor)	is the percentage of the energy demand covered by RE production. It refers to load matching	Leading (simulation), lagging (monitoring)	Ratio between self-consumed energy and total energy use	Sartori I, Napolitano A, Voss K. Net zero energy buildings: a consistent definition framework. Energy Build 2012;48:220–32.	
self-consumption (supply cover factor)	It is the percentage of generated energy which supplies local loads. It refers to load matching.	Leading (simulation), lagging (monitoring)	Ratio between self-consumed energy and energy generation	Analysis of load match and grid interaction indicators in net zero energy buildings with simulated and	

				monitored data. Applied Energy 2014	
Peak export	Power peak (high generation or low load). It refers to grid interaction.	Leading (simulation), lagging (monitoring)			
Peak import	Power peak (low generation or high load). It refers to grid interaction.	Leading (simulation), lagging (monitoring)			

About IEQ, health and well-being, four aspects were analysed: indoor air quality (IAQ), thermal, visual, acoustic, by considering users habits and expectations related to climate context and cultural background. Selected KPIs for IEQ are presented in table 4

Table 4: IEQ KPIs

Aspect	Name	Description	Type	Calculation method	Source	Metric range
IAQ	Supply air flow rate in breathing zone	[l/s per person]	Leading (calculation)	Method 1 based on perceived air quality Method 2 using limit values of gas concentration Method 3 based on predefined ventilation flow rates	CEN, UNI EN 16798	
IAQ	CO2	ppm, maximum value above outdoor concentration	Leading, Lagging (survey)	CO2 levels in the building are to be considered for the calculation of supply air flow rate	CEN, UNI EN 16798	550 ppm above outdoor for Cat. I 800 ppm above outdoor for Cat. II 1350 ppm above outdoor for Cat. III 1350 ppm above outdoor for Cat. IV
IAQ	TVOC	µg/m3, maximum averaged value	Lagging (monitoring)		ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1	
IAQ	Formaldehyde	µg/m3, maximum averaged value	Lagging (monitoring)		ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1	
IAQ	PMs 2.5/10	µg/m3, maximum	Lagging (monitoring)		ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.2	Particulate Matter PM 2.5 15 µg/m3

		averaged value				Particulate Matter PM 10 50 µg/m3
Thermal	% Yearly hours within indoor temperature ranges (°C)		Leading (simulation), Lagging (monitoring)	Temperature ranges for hourly calculation of cooling and heating energy in four categories of indoor environment are prescribed. It is recommended to implement the same methodology for the assessment, but ranges must comply the more specific given classification based on climatic locations (please refer to Cultural-E Atlas for detailed information https://energyatlas.eurac.edu/).	CEN, UNI EN 16798	
Thermal	% Yearly hours within indoor relative humidity ranges (%)		Leading (simulation), Lagging (monitoring)	refer to ASHRAE 55 Comfort Zone Method paragraphs 5.3.1 and 5.3.2 so as to integrate indoor temperature and average air speed.	CEN, UNI EN 16798	RH design setpoints in residential environments generally range from 25 to 60 % (please refer to Cultural-E Atlas for detailed information https://energyatlas.eurac.edu/).

Thermal	Average air speed (m/s)			Air speed shall be considered integrated with indoor air temperature and relative humidity. Occupied zone conditions must also conform to requirements for avoiding local thermal discomfort.	ASHRAE Standard 55	Average air speed design value in residential environments generally <0.20 m/s, with: 1.0 – 1.3 MET 0.5 – 1.0 CLO
Visual	Daylight factor	average % in a room	Leading		CIBSE, Daylighting and Window Design Guide	
Visual	Average illuminance level	average lux according to room activities	Leading		CEN, UNI EN 16798	
Acoustic	Design equivalent continuous sound level	[dB(A)]	Lagging (monitoring)		CEN, UNI EN 16798 - CEN, UNI EN ISO 16032	

Besides Environmental sustainability is considered in the PEB definition, to evaluate Environmental impact in terms of life cycle assessment (LCA) and carbon footprint required specific KPIs, as reported in table 5.

Table 5: Environmental impact KPIs

Name	Description	Type	Calculation method	Source	Metric range
Total GHG emissions (Global Warming Potential)		Leading	<p>GWP= SUM(GWPi x mi) , Where GWPi is Global Warming Potential of substance i [kg of CO2 equivalent/kg] - See formula below; and mi = mass of the substance i inventoried [kg];</p> $GWP_i \equiv \frac{\int_0^{TH} RF_i(t) dt}{\int_0^{TH} RF_r(t) dt} = \frac{\int_0^{TH} a_i \cdot [C_i(t)] dt}{\int_0^{TH} a_r \cdot [C_r(t)] dt}$ <p>Quantity of CO2 eq. emitted by the whole building system over its lifecycle -where CO2 eq is the ratio of the time-integrated radiative forcing from the instantaneous release of 1 kg of a trace substance relative to that of 1 kg of a reference gas</p>	<p>1) IPCC (https://www.ipcc.ch/2019/05/13/ipcc-2019-refinement/)</p> <p>2) EN 15804+A2 (2019)</p> <p>3) Peoportier et at. - LCA state of the art report - European Commission - Europa EU</p>	
GHG emission reduction	Quantity of CO2 eq. emitted by the whole building system over its lifecycle - where CO2 eq is the ratio of the time-integrated radiative forcing from	Leading	<p>GWPr,c= E(produced)*GWP Emix,c /kWh , E is the energy surplus multiplied by the GWP of the considered country electricity mix (please refer to Cultural-E Atlas for detailed information https://energyatlas.eurac.edu/)</p>	EN 15804+A2 (2019)	

	the instantaneous release of 1 kg of a trace substance relative to that of 1 kg of a reference gas				
CO2 emissions - Carbon footprint	Is the individual calculation of the total amount of carbon dioxide (CO2) produced per person through energy consumption.		$CO2 = CO2_{dir} + CO2_{ind}$; where $CO2_{dir} = (Total\ Amount * (CO2\ Emission\ Factor * Heating\ Value) * Density)$ $CO2_{ind} = ((Total\ Amount\ Used\ Based\ on\ Occupancy * Emission\ Factor))$	SHEQ Management System: carbon footprint & global warming potential http://css.umich.edu/factsheets/carbon-footprint-factsheet Jones C., Kammen D. (2011) "Quantifying Carbon Footprint Reduction Opportunities for U.S. Households and Communities." https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.09.040	

A set of indicators for economic impact in terms of life cycle costs of PEH was selected as reported in table 6.

Table 6: Economic impact KPIs

Name	Description	Type	Calculation method	Source	Metric range
Investment cost	all costs that need to be covered until an energy efficiency measure is fully implemented	Leading	Investment cost for preparation measures, building construction and building services construction (Cost Group 200, 300, 400): Total amount: €, specific cost per unit: €/unit specific cost per m ² : €/m ²	German DIN 276 building cost	
Energy cost, operational cost	is the annual operation cost of the energy resources in the building	Leading, Lagging (monitoring)	Energy demand for final energy from thermal simulation or energy balance according to national code. Local energy prices. Compiled with maintenance cost to the operational cost: Total amount: €/a specific cost monthly per unit: €/(unit*month) specific cost monthly per m ² : €/(m ² *month)	DIN EN 15459-1	
Maintenance cost	maintenance and service cost for technical building services: heating, cooling, ventilation, electricity from PV (not user appliances)	Leading, Lagging (verify if small compared to investment)	yearly percentage of investment, included in Operational cost	DIN EN 15459-1	
Pay Back Period (PBP) of additional invest (over reference)	is the time it takes to cover additional investment cost compared to baseline building (nZEB)	Leading	The payback period is the time it takes to cover investment costs. It is calculated as the number of years elapsed between the initial investment, its subsequent operating costs and the time at which cumulative savings offset the investment. When assessing the	following ISO 15686-5, VDI 2067, DIN EN 15459-1	

			viability of alternatives, the payback period is the time it takes to recoup the initial investment of one alternative relative to another.		
Life-Cycle Cost (LCC)	the present value of the total cost of building usage for the whole calculation period	Leading	Phases Construction, Operation, Maintenance, Environmental cost. End of life not included	following ISO 15686-5,	
Net-Present-Value (NPV)		Leading	The net present value (NPV) may be described as the sum of the discounted benefit of an alternative less the sum of the discounted costs.	following ISO 15686-5, VDI 2067, DIN EN 15459-1	
Total Cost of Ownership	including investment cost, operational cost (energy and maintenance) cost for replacement after end of life. Cost are discounted cost	Leading	Total cost in €/a, specific cost per area $\text{€}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{a})$	following ISO 15686-5, VDI 2067, DIN EN 15459-1	

Selected social impact KPIs, reported in table 7. Most of them rely on user perspective and are related to surveys.

Table 7: Social impact KPIs

Name	Description	Type	Calculation method	Source	Metric range
Consumer engagement	Measures the involvement of users in the control over the energy use in the building.	Lagging	Combination of several inputs depending on Application and its functions. Main inputs are frequency of usage, depth of usage, specific actions taken, clickstream information, key performance indicators	https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/14/4/1113 https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=9233110 SaaS	
Social compatibility	The extent to which the building solutions fit with people frame of mind			Pol, E., and D. Carro. "New Energy Sources, New Conflicts: Some Reflections on the Social Impact and the Acceptance of Alternative Energy Sources." In Urban Diversities, Biosphere and Well-Being: Designing and Managing Our Common Environment (IAPS 20 Conference Proceedings on CD-Rom). IAPS. Rome, Italy: Aula Magna Sapienza University of Rome, 2008.; Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) ; https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=8718592 ;	
Ease of use for end users	The extent to which the solution is perceived as	Lagging		https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=8718592 ;	

	difficult to understand and use				
Advantages for end-users	The extent to which the project offers clear advantages for end users. The advantage can take many forms, for instance cost savings, improved quality and increased comfort.	Leading	interviews, listing of verified advantages		
Advantages for stakeholder	The extent to which the project offers clear advantages for stakeholders. This advantage could, for example, be ease of management or reduced	Leading	interviews, listing of verified advantages		

	maintenance costs.				
People reached	Percentage of people in the target group that have been reached and/or are activated by the project.	Leading, Lagging	(active group participant/total group participants)%	The Persona Lifecycle: Keeping People in Mind Throughout Product Design, John Pruitt, Tamara Adlin	
Local job creation	an indicator to assess the Creation of direct jobs from the implementation and operation of the respective solutions.	Leading, Lagging	Number of new jobs in the considered region per year for all sectors. Please note: in 2) municipalities are considered while most of study consider the local area of a country. The local boundaries depends on the goal of the analysis	Guide on Measuring Decent Jobs for Youth Monitoring, evaluation and learning in labour market programmes; Volume 2 Concepts and definitions of employment indicators relevant to young people; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2009.07.013	

Finally, smart readiness indicator (SRI) is included as a KPI, to determine the predisposition of buildings to "smartness", i.e. the ability to improve energy efficiency and overall performance and to improve interaction with the users and surrounding infrastructures. Smart readiness impacts different domains like heating, cooling, controlled ventilation, demand side management (DSM), domestic hot water, dynamic building envelope, electric vehicle charging, energy generation, monitoring and control and others. Further information on SRI can be found here: <https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator>

6 Conclusion

The deliverable presented results from a comprehensive literature review of existing PEB definition and evaluation approaches. In the literature, definitions and requirements are generic, and the assessment approaches are not consistent in key issues to be considered while evaluating PEB. The lack of standardization results in difficulties in comparing this type of building across different countries.

A robust and holistic definition of PEB is given by according to Cultural-E approach, which takes into account the positive energy balance, cost affordability and environmental sustainability. The definition directly translates into a suggestion to policy strategy roadmap and market penetration of PEB concepts.

A consistent evaluation framework for the evaluation of solution sets for PEBs is outlined. Appropriate leading and lagging KPIs have been selected from literature and corresponding calculation methodologies are reported and referenced.

An open access paper was developed and included as Annex I. This study reviewed and discussed the widely used metric for evaluating PEB, balancing period, the type of energy included in the balance, the type of balance and the RE supply options, as well as other parameters related to the interaction between the building and the environment, the user and the energy grid, as well as social and economic aspects. The Cultural-E approach is presented and discussed.

ANNEX I – Open Access paper

The open access paper “Plus energy building: Operational definition and assessment” published on the Energy & Buildings journal is available at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.112069>.

The open access paper is also available as an attachment to this document.